

Research Article

Performance Evaluation of a Radial Distribution Network Under Emerging Load Prediction Modeling Approach and DG Integration Using a Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm

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This research presents a comprehensive performance evaluation of an 11-bus, 15 kV radial distribution network in Ethiopia, utilizing particle swarm optimization (PSO) to assess the impact of emerging load prediction models and distributed generation (DG) integration. Load forecasting is conducted using the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), with validation carried out through an artificial neural network (ANN). The average forecasted load predicted by ANFIS is 6,071.5 kVA, compared to 6,105.7 kVA by ANN. The accuracy of these forecasts is quantified by mean absolute error (MAE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2), where ANFIS demonstrates superior performance with a MAE = 7.7611, MAPE = 0.14401, MSE = 0.6399, RMSE = 0.79993, and $R^2 = 0.99993$, in contrast to ANN's MAE = 31.4114, MAPE = 1.631%, MSE = 109.55, RMSE = 10.467, and $R^2 = 0.98797$. The study further examines the network's operational efficiency in terms of power loss, voltage stability index (VSI), average voltage deviation index (AVDI), loss of load probability (LOLP), energy not supplied (ENS), and average energy not supplied (AENS). These performance metrics are evaluated under various load conditions, including base load and forecasted loads derived from both ANN and ANFIS predictions, incorporating DG integration. The results highlight that the PSO algorithm excels in optimizing network performance, achieving remarkable results across all evaluated parameters. Despite these promising findings, the study has certain limitations. The proposed model assumes ideal DG operation without considering uncertainties in renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power variations. Additionally, the impact of network reconfiguration and real-time control strategies for dynamic load variations is not fully explored. The computational complexity of integrating ANFIS-based forecasting with large-scale networks poses a challenge, requiring further optimization for practical applications. Future research should address these challenges by incorporating probabilistic models for DG output fluctuations, real-time network reconfiguration techniques, and hybrid optimization approaches for enhanced scalability and adaptability.

Keywords: adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system; artificial neural network; average voltage deviation index; load forecasting; loss of load probability; particle swarm optimization; radial distribution network

1. Introduction

The demand for efficient and reliable electrical power distribution has never been more critical, especially as the complexity of power networks increases due to emerging technologies and load dynamics. The radial distribution

network (RDN), a common topology in power systems, offers simplicity and reliability but faces challenges in performance optimization and load management. This study focuses on an 11-bus, 15 kV RDN in Ethiopia, evaluating its performance under various load prediction scenarios using advanced forecasting and optimization techniques.

Accurate load forecasting is fundamental to effective network operation and planning. Traditional methods often fail to capture the intricate and uncertain nature of load variations. Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) and artificial neural networks (ANNs) have emerged as reliable tools to address these complexities. ANFIS combines the adaptability of neural networks with the reasoning capabilities of fuzzy logic, effectively modeling nonlinear and complex relationships [1–5]. Meanwhile, ANNs leverage their layered structure and adaptive learning to provide high accuracy in diverse scenarios [6]. Recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of these methods in energy systems, showcasing their ability to improve load prediction and enhance network planning [7, 8]. In this research, ANFIS is used for load forecasting and validated against ANN models, with forecasted values compared using metrics such as root mean squared error (RMSE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). These metrics offer critical insights into the models' accuracy and their implications for network performance. The evaluation of network performance incorporates particle swarm optimization (PSO), an optimization algorithm inspired by the social behavior of organisms like birds and fish. PSO is applied to assess critical performance parameters, including power loss, voltage stability, power quality, and network reliability, particularly under scenarios involving distributed generation (DG) integration [9, 10].

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the RDN's performance by integrating advanced forecasting models with optimization techniques. The results underscore the effectiveness of ANFIS and ANN in load prediction and highlight the potential of PSO to optimize network performance. By addressing the challenges in load forecasting and network optimization, this research contributes to the development of more reliable and efficient power distribution systems.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3 details the methodology of the research. Section 4 presents the simulation results and discusses the performance improvements achieved. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of findings.

2. Literature Review

The performance evaluation of RDNs is a critical area of study in power systems engineering, especially with the increasing complexity brought by emerging load prediction models and the integration of DG resources. PSO algorithms have emerged as a popular tool for optimizing such systems. This literature review explores recent advancements in evaluating the performance of RDNs, focusing on load prediction, DG integration, and the application of PSO algorithms.

2.1. RDNs. RDNs are widely used in electrical power systems due to their straightforward architecture and ease of implementation as shown in Figure 1 [11]. These networks

FIGURE 1: A sample radial distribution network [11].

are characterized by a single source feeding multiple load points along a single path [11–13]. While their simplicity reduces operational complexity and costs, it also introduces challenges, especially under varying load conditions [14–17]. Several studies highlight the operational characteristics of radial systems, including their power quality, power system stability, reliability, and efficiency [18–20].

The primary challenges associated with RDNs include voltage drops, power losses, and reduced reliability [18–21]. Voltage drop is a significant concern as it affects the quality of power supplied to end users. Power loss in these networks is a result of the resistance in the feeder lines and is exacerbated by increasing load levels [21–25]. A study by Ghosh et al. [26] highlighted the importance of addressing these issues to improve the efficiency and reliability of radial networks. Muñoz-Delgado et al. [27] also outlined how radial systems typically exhibit lower reliability due to their susceptibility to disruptions; a fault in any part of the system can lead to a loss of service for all downstream loads. Conversely, their simplicity often translates to lower maintenance costs and ease of operation.

Recent advancements in network design and control have focused on integrating DG sources and implementing advanced control strategies to mitigate the inherent limitations of radial networks [28–34]. A research by Parhizi et al. [35] also discusses various strategies for enhancing the performance of RDNs, including the integration of renewable energy sources and the use of advanced monitoring and control technologies.

2.2. Load Forecasting Techniques. Accurate load forecasting is crucial for the efficient planning and operation of power distribution systems. Predicting future load demands allows utilities to optimize network performance, reduce operational costs, and ensure reliable service delivery [21, 36, 37]. Traditional load forecasting methods, such as autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA), autoregressive moving average (ARMA), and exponential smoothing, have been widely used due to their simplicity and effectiveness in modeling linear time-series data [38–40]. However, these

statistical methods often struggle to capture the complex, nonlinear, and dynamic nature of electricity consumption patterns, necessitating the adoption of more advanced forecasting techniques [41–43].

Recent advancements in intelligent and deep learning-based load forecasting models have significantly improved prediction accuracy and adaptability. Computational intelligence techniques, including fuzzy systems, fuzzy-PSO, fuzzy-genetic algorithm (GA), ANFIS, and ANNs, have emerged as powerful alternatives due to their capability to model intricate, nonlinear relationships in load data [44–49].

ANFIS is a hybrid model that integrates fuzzy logic with neural networks, combining the interpretability of fuzzy inference systems with the adaptive learning capabilities of neural networks. Jang [50] initially introduced ANFIS as a framework that merges rule-based fuzzy logic with neural network training to optimize system parameters. ANFIS utilizes fuzzy rules to encode expert knowledge and employs neural networks to refine these rules, enabling it to manage uncertainties and adapt to varying load patterns. Khedher et al. [51] validated the effectiveness of ANFIS in load forecasting, emphasizing its adaptability and robustness in managing fluctuating demand profiles. Further studies by Zhang et al. [52] integrated ANFIS with optimization algorithms such as GAs and PSO, significantly improving forecasting accuracy. Additionally, Chen and Li [53] demonstrated that combining ANFIS with deep learning techniques enhanced its ability to model complex load dynamics, making it a reliable forecasting tool in modern power systems. Wang et al. [54] conducted a comparative study of ANFIS and other modern forecasting techniques, concluding that ANFIS, due to its hybrid nature, outperforms many traditional and contemporary models in forecasting accuracy.

ANNs have also gained prominence in load forecasting due to their ability to learn complex, nonlinear relationships from historical data. Deep learning architectures, such as long short-term memory (LSTM) networks, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and hybrid deep learning models, have further improved forecasting performance [55–57]. Zhang et al. [58] developed an advanced ANN model for short-term load forecasting, demonstrating superior accuracy in capturing intricate consumption patterns. Hossain et al. [59] conducted a comparative study on different ANN architectures, highlighting the advantages of deep neural networks in handling nonstationary load profiles. Patel et al. [60] explored the integration of ANNs with ensemble learning methods, such as random forest and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), demonstrating enhanced prediction accuracy and resilience to data variability. Moreover, hybrid models that integrate deep learning techniques with traditional methods have been explored to further enhance forecasting accuracy. LSTM-CNN hybrid models have been successfully applied to load forecasting, leveraging LSTM's sequential learning capability and CNN's feature extraction efficiency [55]. Reinforcement learning-based approaches have also emerged as promising solutions, particularly in real-time load prediction and demand-side management [61].

In conclusion, the evolution of intelligent and deep learning-based load forecasting techniques has significantly improved prediction accuracy and adaptability. Hybrid models, optimization-driven ANFIS frameworks, deep learning-based architectures, and ensemble methods have demonstrated superior performance over traditional approaches. Future research should focus on further integrating reinforcement learning, transfer learning, and federated learning to address challenges such as data scarcity, computational complexity, and real-time adaptability in load forecasting.

2.3. Optimal Operation of Radial Power Distribution Systems.

Optimization techniques are essential for improving the performance of power distribution networks by minimizing key metrics such as power loss and voltage deviations. PSO, introduced by Kennedy and Eberhart [62], is a heuristic optimization algorithm inspired by the social behaviors of birds and fish. It is widely used to find optimal solutions in complex and multidimensional spaces. PSO has been applied to various optimization problems in power systems due to its simplicity and effectiveness. Shi and Eberhart [63] demonstrated the utility of PSO in optimizing network configurations, reducing power losses, and enhancing voltage stability. In their study, they highlighted PSO's capability to converge rapidly while effectively exploring the solution space for optimal configurations, making it an effective tool for large-scale distribution network optimization.

The integration of PSO with forecasting models such as the ANFIS and ANNs enhances the optimization process by incorporating accurate load predictions. This hybrid approach allows for the efficient adjustment of network parameters based on forecasted load profiles, ensuring better adaptability to dynamic conditions. Recent studies [64–67] show that combining PSO with advanced forecasting techniques improves network performance significantly. For example, these methods have led to reduced power losses and enhanced voltage stability by optimizing network configuration and ensuring accurate load forecasting. This integration offers a more comprehensive evaluation of network performance under varying load scenarios, crucial for ensuring the resilience and efficiency of power distribution systems.

Several studies have applied hybrid PSO forecasting approaches to various optimization problems. Vasant et al. [68] employed ANFIS combined with PSO for optimal capacitor placement in radial distribution systems, showing substantial reductions in system losses and improvements in voltage profiles. Similarly, Shakeri and Zareipour [69] utilized a hybrid PSO-ANN model to optimize the placement of DG sources, demonstrating improved overall system efficiency and reliability. These studies reinforce the potential of hybrid models to optimize key parameters in power distribution networks, showcasing their contribution to the advancement of energy systems.

Beyond the classic PSO-ANN and PSO-ANFIS hybrids, newer hybrid optimization algorithms have gained traction in the optimization of DG integration. For example, the

integration of PSO with GAs has been widely studied for its enhanced exploration and exploitation capabilities in complex optimization landscapes. Yu et al. [70] demonstrated a hybrid PSO-GA algorithm to optimize DG placement and sizing, resulting in significant reductions in power losses and enhanced voltage stability in distribution networks. This hybrid method combines the global search capabilities of PSO with the fine-tuning precision of GA, offering an efficient solution for DG integration in radial systems.

Another promising hybrid method is the combination of PSO and differential evolution (DE), which has shown substantial benefits in optimizing DG placement and minimizing operational costs. Li et al. [71] applied a PSO-DE hybrid model to determine the optimal location and size of DG units in a distribution network, achieving significant reductions in network losses and voltage deviations. The hybrid approach utilized the strengths of both PSO and DE, with PSO providing global search capabilities and DE excelling in local refinement.

Moreover, the integration of deep learning techniques with PSO has recently emerged as a powerful tool for DG optimization. Li et al. [72] developed a hybrid PSO-deep learning algorithm for optimal DG placement, where deep learning models were used for accurate load forecasting and PSO was employed for optimal DG placement. The results indicated that this hybrid approach could effectively handle the uncertainties in load demand and improve the reliability and efficiency of power distribution systems.

Furthermore, the combination of PSO with ant colony optimization (ACO) has been explored for optimizing DG placement, particularly in systems with multiple DG sources. Wang and Li [73] proposed a PSO-ACO hybrid algorithm to minimize power losses and optimize the voltage profile of distribution networks with multiple DG units. This hybrid approach capitalizes on the exploration capabilities of PSO and the exploitation features of ACO, leading to improved network performance.

These advancements in hybrid algorithms not only improve the optimization of DG placement and sizing but also contribute to the broader goal of optimizing overall system performance, enhancing power quality, and ensuring the reliability of power distribution networks under dynamic load conditions. These case studies highlight the effectiveness of integrating forecasting models with optimization techniques to address the challenges associated with RDNs. The application of these techniques to Ethiopian power systems, particularly in the context of RDNs, is relatively underexplored. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating the performance of an 11-bus, 15 kV Ethiopian RDN using ANFIS for load forecasting and PSO for network optimization.

3. Methodology

The methodology for this study is designed to evaluate the performance of an 11-bus, 15 kV Ethiopian RDN by integrating advanced load forecasting models and optimization techniques. The approach involves load forecasting

using ANFIS and ANN, followed by performance analysis of the network under various load scenarios using PSO in MATLAB environment.

3.1. Study Network Description

3.1.1. Network Configuration. The study focuses on an 11-bus, 15 kV RDN typical of Ethiopian power systems. This network consists of buses, distribution lines, and transformers configured in a radial topology, as shown in Figure 2. The average total system load connected to the radial distribution system is 6,029.9 kVA, while the peak and valley load values are recorded as 8,727.1 and 4,123.6 kVA, respectively.

3.1.2. Data Collection and Analysis. Network parameters, including bus voltages, line impedances, and transformer ratings, are collected and prepared for simulation. Additionally, temperature, tariff, and historical load data are collected to develop load forecasting models. For an effective load demand forecast, two distinct datasets are essential: the training dataset and the testing dataset. Both the load data and weather information are sourced from an 11-bus, 15 kV RDN in Ethiopia. Hourly load data spanning four years, from 2019 to 2023, are collected. The data from the first three years are utilized to train the load forecasting model, while the data from the final year are employed to assess the model's performance. ANFIS and ANN prediction algorithms are utilized to model the load forecast. The model is developed and implemented within the MATLAB software environment.

Both the training and testing load datasets are formatted to represent 24 h periods, derived from the raw historical load data collected from the case study area using the following equation:

$$P_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T L_t, \quad (1)$$

where P_i is the average load in the i th hour, which is computed using the average value of the available load data size in a similar time frame. T is the total load data size in days, and it is 365 for the validation dataset, but 730 for the training load dataset. L_t is the industrial load in the i th hour of t th day.

Figure 3 presents the average hourly load data over three years for training and one year for testing.

3.2. Load Forecasting Models. This article presents the development of a load prediction model utilizing the ANFIS. Additionally, an ANN model is employed as a validation technique to assess the performance of the proposed ANFIS model. The process of developing the ANFIS load prediction model encompasses three fundamental stages: data preparation, model training using historical datasets, and validation of the proposed model.

3.2.1. ANFIS. ANFIS combines the adaptive capabilities of neural networks with the interpretability of fuzzy logic to forecast future loads based on historical data as illustrated in

FIGURE 2: A typical 11 bus, 15 kV radial distribution system in Ethiopia.

FIGURE 3: Training and testing load data pattern.

Figure 4. This hybrid approach allows for more accurate load predictions by leveraging the strengths of both methods. The process begins with preprocessing the historical load data, which includes normalization and the division of data into training and testing subsets. The input layer of an ANFIS system is responsible for receiving and preprocessing the input variables from the dataset. In this layer, raw data values are introduced into the system. Each input variable is fed into the network without modification, ensuring that the raw data are preserved for subsequent processing. This layer serves as the initial conduit through which all data enters the ANFIS framework. The fuzzification layer, on the other hand, is where the crisp input values are converted into fuzzy sets. This transformation is achieved through the application of membership functions that map the input data into degrees of membership within various fuzzy sets. Each input is evaluated against predefined fuzzy membership functions, which classify the inputs into linguistic terms such as “high,”

“medium,” or “low.” This layer captures the inherent uncertainty and imprecision of the real-world data by representing it in fuzzy terms, facilitating more nuanced modeling.

The normalization layer standardizes the output from the fuzzification layer to ensure that all values are within a specified range, typically between 0 and 1. This normalization process is crucial for maintaining the consistency and stability of the subsequent computations. By scaling the data, the normalization layer enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of the fuzzy inference rules applied in the following stages, ensuring that the model’s outputs are not disproportionately influenced by varying magnitudes of input values. The defuzzification layer is responsible for converting the fuzzy outputs back into crisp, actionable values. This process involves aggregating the fuzzy outputs obtained from the inference process and translating them into a single representative value. Various defuzzification methods, such

FIGURE 4: ANFIS structure.

as the centroid method, are employed to achieve this. This layer effectively synthesizes the fuzzy conclusions derived from the inference engine into a precise, actionable output that can be used for practical decision making. The output layer of an ANFIS system is the final stage where the defuzzified results are produced. It provides the system's final predictions or decisions based on the processed data. The output values, derived from the defuzzification layer, are presented as concrete results that reflect the system's conclusions. This layer represents the culmination of the fuzzy inference process, delivering the refined outputs that inform the user or subsequent processes.

The ANFIS model is then trained using the training dataset. This involves configuring fuzzy inference rules and membership functions to accurately capture load patterns and predict future demand. The model's performance is evaluated by validating it with the testing dataset and comparing the results with those obtained from an ANN load prediction model. Performance is assessed based on forecast accuracy metrics using RMSE and MAPE. Figure 4 demonstrates the ANFIS architecture.

3.2.2. ANNs. ANNs are computational models inspired by the human brain's structure and function. They consist of interconnected nodes or "neurons," organized into three layers (input layer, hidden layer, and output layer) as shown in Figure 5, which work collaboratively to process input data and generate output predictions. Similar preprocessing steps are applied as in ANFIS, with data divided into training and validation sets. Values of the training and testing input and output datasets are encoded with the neurons and the ANN load prediction model is developed and trained using the Bayesian regularization algorithms to optimize the network architecture, including the number of layers and neurons.

Neurons apply a sigmoid activation function (f) to the weighted sum of their inputs to determine the neuron's output. The output of each layer using the parameters (x_i

and w_i) of the input variable and the bias (w_{oi}) is computed using equations (2) and (3).

$$f(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-Z}}, \quad (2)$$

$$Z = w_{oi} + \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times X_i, \quad (3)$$

where w_{oi} is the weight of the bias and w_i is the weight of the input variable X_i which are computed from the fitness function during the training process of the ANN at each iteration.

Figure 6 illustrates the application of the ANN algorithm for load forecasting.

3.2.3. Prediction Accuracy Measure. The accuracy level of the load prediction models is measured using the mean absolute error (MAE), MAPE, mean squared error (MSE), RMSE, and the coefficient of determination (R-squared, R^2). These five essential regression parameters are evaluated using the forecasted and testing dataset values using equations (3)–(8), respectively.

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 5: Architecture of ANN.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2}, \quad (8)$$

where y_i represents the testing datasets, \hat{y}_i represents the forecasted load datasets, $\bar{y}_i = (1/n)\sum_{i=1}^n y_i$ is the mean of the actual data, and n is the forecasting time horizon or data size.

3.3. Performance Evaluation Using PSO

3.3.1. Load Scenarios. The performance of an 11-bus, 15 kV radial distribution system is evaluated under current load conditions without relying on load forecasting models. The evaluation involves utilizing load forecasts generated by ANFIS and ANN models to understand their impact on system performance. This approach provides insights into how predictive models might influence distribution system analysis. Additionally, the study incorporates the integration of DG into the radial distribution system, assessing how various levels of DG influence system stability, reliability, and efficiency. By analyzing these factors, the evaluation aims to identify optimal strategies for enhancing system performance and managing load variations effectively.

3.3.2. The Radial Distribution System Performance Metrics. The reliability, power quality, power system stability, and efficiency improvement of the radial distribution system are the objectives to achieve. The total power loss, loss of load probability (LOLP), energy not supplied (ENS), average energy not supplied (AENS), average voltage deviation index (AVDI), and voltage stability index (VSI) are considered as crucial indicators to measure the performance of a radial distribution system, and these metrics are determined from the steady-state load flow analysis of the radial distribution system. All the performance metrics mentioned above are evaluated from an “ n ” bus radial distribution system presented in Figure 7.

3.3.2.1. Network Power Loss. The active and reactive power losses across all the branches are computed using the branch

impedances and branch current using equations (9) and (10), respectively. The real and reactive line loss between bus k and $k+1$ is computed using the following equations [74–77].

$$P_{\text{loss}}(k, k+1) = R_k \frac{P_k^2 + Q_k^2}{V_k^2}, \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{\text{loss}}(k, k+1) = X_k \frac{P_k^2 + Q_k^2}{V_k^2}. \quad (10)$$

The total active ($P_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1)$) and reactive ($Q_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1)$) power loss of the whole feeder in the distribution network is computed using equations (11) and (12), respectively.

$$P_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1) = \sum_{k=1}^n P_{\text{loss}}(k, k+1), \quad (11)$$

$$Q_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1) = \sum_{k=1}^n Q_{\text{loss}}(k, k+1), \quad (12)$$

where k is the bus number, P_k and Q_k are active and reactive power flows, respectively, R_k and X_k are the feeder resistance and reactance values, respectively, and $P_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1)$ and $Q_{T,\text{loss}}(k, k+1)$ are the total active and reactive power loss of all branches connecting buses k and $k+1$, respectively.

3.3.2.2. LOLP. LOLP measures the frequency with which a system generation $P_G(t)$ fails to meet the load demand $P_L(t)$, or the average percentage of load that the system cannot fulfill. It is calculated as the ratio of the total energy deficit to the total load demand over a given period. LOLP can be defined as [78]

$$\text{LOLP} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T P_L(t) - \sum_{t=1}^T P_G(t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T P_L(t)}, \quad (13)$$

where $P_G(t)$ and $P_L(t)$ are total system generation and total load demand, respectively.

FIGURE 6: ANN algorithm flowchart for load prediction.

FIGURE 7: Sample radial distribution system for performance analysis.

3.3.2.3. *ENS*. The ENS is a measure of the total amount of electrical energy that a power system fails to deliver to its customers due to generation shortages or system failures. It quantifies the shortfall in energy supply during a period when the demand exceeds the available generation capacity. It reflects the reliability of the power system in meeting the demand [79]. It is computed using the following equation.

$$\text{ENS} = \sum_{k=1, i=1}^T P_{Li}(t) \times T_{ok} - \left(P_{DG} \times \sum_{k=1, i=1}^T T_{ok} + \sum_{k=1, i=1}^T (P_{Gi}(t) \times T_{ok}) \right), \quad (14)$$

where $P_{Li}(t)$ is the demand of the i th node, $P_{Gi}(t)$ is the generation at the i th node, T_{ok} is the outage time of the k th feeder, and T is the total number of feeders.

3.3.2.4. *AENS*. AENS is a metric that quantifies the average amount of energy that a power system fails to deliver to each customer over a specified period. It serves as an indicator of the system's reliability by measuring the typical shortfall in energy supply experienced by each customer when the generation capacity falls short of the demand. Mathematically, AENS is calculated as the total ENS divided by the total number of customers connected to the network during the specified period. This can be expressed using the following formula [79].

$$\text{AENS} = \frac{\sum_{k=1, i=1}^T P_{Li}(t) \times T_{ok} - \left(P_{DG} \times \sum_{k=1, i=1}^T T_{ok} + \sum_{k=1, i=1}^T (P_{Gi}(t) \times T_{ok}) \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N C_i}, \quad (15)$$

where $P_{Li}(t)$ is the demand of the i th node, $P_{Gi}(t)$ is the generation at the i th node, T_{ok} is the outage time of the k th feeder, T is the number of feeders, C_i is the number of customers connected in the i th node, and N is the total number of nodes.

3.3.2.5. *VSI*. The VSI is a measure of the stability of a power system when an intermittent renewable energy resource like solar and wind-based microgrid is connected to a radial distribution system. The VSI is computed from the radial distribution system given in Figure 7 as in [80]:

$$\text{VSI} = \left[V_k^4 - 4P_{k+1}(X_{k,k+1} + R_{k,k+1}) + Q_{k+1}(X_{k,k+1}V_k^2 - R_{k,k+1}^2) \right], \quad (16)$$

where k is the node number, V_o and V_k are the nominal voltage and the actual voltage of the k 's bus, P_{k+1} and Q_{k+1} are the net active and reactive power at bus $k+1$, and $R_{k,k+1}$ and $X_{k,k+1}$ are the feeder resistance and reactance connecting buses k and $k+1$.

3.3.2.6. *AVDI*. The AVDI is a measure of the quality of power generated from the supplier and supplied to an electricity customer. It is a measure of the mean absolute voltage difference between the nominal voltage (1.0 p.u) and the actual bus voltages at all nodes of the radial distribution system. The AVDI is calculated from the radial distribution system in Figure 7 [81]:

$$\text{AVDI} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |V_o - V_k|^2, \quad (17)$$

where n is the number of buses in the RDN and V_o and V_k are the nominal voltage and the actual voltage of the k 's bus.

3.3.3. *Objective Function Formulation*. The fitness function is a measure of the performance of a radial power distribution

network. The objective is to improve the efficiency, the power quality, the reliability, and the stability of the radial power distribution system during DG system integration under different load scenario. The overall system power loss ($P_{T,loss}$), the LOLP, ENS, AENS, AVDI, and VSI are the six performance metrics considered for the performance evaluation of the RDN. All the objective functions except the VSI should be minimized while the VSI needs to be maximized. f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5 , and f_6 are objective functions representing the total system power loss, LOLP, ENS, AENS, AVDI, and VSI, respectively. Therefore, the fitness function contains a combination of both minimizing and maximizing objectives, as represented in equations (18)–(23).

$$f_1(V_k, P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \min(P_{T,loss}, Q_{T,loss}), \quad (18)$$

$$f_2(P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \min(\text{LOLP}), \quad (19)$$

$$f_3(P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \min(\text{ENS}), \quad (20)$$

$$f_4(P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \min(\text{AENS}), \quad (21)$$

$$f_5(V_k, P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \min(\text{AVDI}), \quad (22)$$

$$f_6(V_k, P_{DG}, Q_{DG}) = \max(\text{VSI}). \quad (23)$$

This is a multiobjective optimization problem (MOOP) to find the optimal solution of more than one desired goal. The first objective function is denoted as $f_1(x)$ which is the power loss in the system, the second objective function, $f_2(x)$, is the LOLP, $f_3(x)$ is the ENS, $f_4(x)$ is the AENS, $f_5(x)$ is the AVDI, and $f_6(x)$ is the VSI of the radial distribution system; then the MOOP is formulated using the following equation:

$$\text{minimize } f\{f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x), f_4(x), f_5(x), f_6(x)\}. \quad (24)$$

The scalarization approach is applied to convert the multiobjective optimization function into a single objective function and the weighting factor, w_i , of each function is determined before the optimization process. The fitness function is represented in the following equation.

$$f = w_1 f_1 + w_2 f_2 + w_3 f_3 + w_4 f_4 + w_5 f_5 + w_6 \frac{1}{f_6}. \quad (25)$$

The weighting factor can be calculated based on the dominance (the degree of importance) characteristics of each objective function.

3.3.4. Constraint Formulation. The bus voltage limit, the power balance between generation and load, the short circuit current limit of the feeder, and the DG capacity limits are considered as constraint parameters for the formulation of the objective function problem.

3.3.5. PSO. The PSO algorithm is employed to optimize network performance parameters such as power loss, VSI, AVDI, LOLP, ENS, and AENS. The implementation of the PSO algorithm in the performance evaluation of the RDN is demonstrated in Figure 8. The PSO algorithm is summarized in the following five steps [48, 49, 62, 63, 82].

Step 1: Initialize PSO parameters $[\omega, c_1, c_2, r_1, r_2]$.

Step 2: Random generation of initial solution in the search space (velocity and position of each particle is randomly initialized) and evaluation of the fitness function from the initial solution in order to determine the personal best and global best particle in the population.

Step 3: Update the velocity and position of each particle using the following formula.

$$V_{id}^{t+1} = \omega V_{id}^t + c_1 r_1 (P_{id}^t - x_{id}^t) + c_2 r_2 (G_d^t - x_{id}^t), \quad (26)$$

$$x_{id}^{t+1} = x_{id}^t + V_{id}^{t+1}. \quad (27)$$

Step 4: Update the personal best and global best position of the particle at each iteration.

$$P_{id}^{t+1} = x_{id}^{t+1} \text{ if } f[X_k(t+1)] \leq f[P_k^b(t)], \quad (28)$$

$$G_k^b(t+1) = X_k(t+1) \text{ if } f[X_k(t+1)] \leq f[G_k^b(t)]. \quad (29)$$

Step 5: Go to Step 3 when the termination criterion is not satisfied; otherwise, terminate the PSO algorithm. f is the fitness function, t is the current iteration, c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration coefficients, r_1 and r_2 are evenly distributed random numbers in the range 0-1, and P_{id}^t and G_d^t are the personal best and global best positions of the particles from the population.

PSO relies on carefully selected parameters to balance exploration and exploitation, directly influencing convergence speed and solution quality. These parameters include termination criteria, swarm size, inertia weight, and cognitive and social acceleration coefficients. The inertia weight (ω) regulates the trade-off between exploration (global search) and exploitation (local search) in the PSO algorithm [62, 63]. Higher values (0.9–1.2) promote exploration, preventing premature convergence, while lower values (0.3–0.6) enhance exploitation, improving local refinement but increasing the risk of getting trapped in local minima. To achieve an optimal balance between exploration and exploitation, an adaptive or linearly decreasing inertia weight, as expressed in equation (27), is often employed. On the other hand, the acceleration coefficients, both cognitive (c_1) and social (c_2), determine how much a particle relies on its own experience and how much it is influenced by its neighbors, respectively. Equations (28) and (29) ensure a balance between a particle's individual experience and the collective influence of neighboring particles. Additionally, swarm size and termination criteria play crucial roles in determining the convergence rate and the quality of the results [83, 84].

The control of the inertia weight (ω), the cognitive (c_1), and social (c_2) acceleration coefficients will improve the performance of PSO algorithm in various application. A mutation strategy to avoid the premature convergence to local optimum of PSO algorithm is proposed by Li et al. [85]. In this research, premature convergence of the PSO algorithm is avoided using a method proposed by Ratnaweera et al. [86]. This method requires less computational time, is easy to implement, and can be integrated into the basic PSO algorithm. According to [87], a linearly increasing social acceleration factor and a linearly decreasing cognitive acceleration factor assist in boosting the global searching capability while balancing the local searching ability of the particles in the multidimensional search space. The inertia weight (ω), cognitive acceleration factor (c_1), and social acceleration factors (c_2) are computed at every iteration using equations (30)–(32) and later incorporated to the PSO algorithm in MATLAB programming.

$$\omega(t) = \omega_{\max} - \frac{(\omega_{\max} - \omega_{\min}) \times t}{I_t}, \quad (30)$$

$$c_1(t) = c_{1\max} + \frac{(c_{1\min} - c_{1\max}) \times t}{I_t}, \quad (31)$$

$$c_2(t) = c_{2\max} + \frac{(c_{2\max} - c_{2\min}) \times t}{I_t}, \quad (32)$$

where t is the current iteration, I_t is the total number of iteration, $\omega_{\max} = 0.99$ is the maximum inertia weight, $\omega_{\min} = 0.1$ is the minimum inertia weight, $c_{1\min} = 0.25$ is the minimum value of cognitive acceleration factor, $c_{1\max} = 2.5$ is the maximum value of cognitive acceleration factor, $c_{2\min} = 0.25$ is the minimum value of social acceleration factor, and $c_{2\max} = 2.5$ is the maximum value of social acceleration factor.

FIGURE 8: Implementation of PSO for optimal evaluation of radial distribution system.

4. Simulation Results and Discussion

4.1. Introduction. This section presents the detailed results obtained from simulating the 11-bus, 15 kV RDN under various load scenarios using ANFIS and ANNs for load forecasting. PSO is utilized to assess the network performance in terms of power loss, VSI, AVDI, LOLP, ENS, and AENS.

4.2. Load Forecasting Results

4.2.1. ANFIS. In this study, the average total system load connected to the radial distribution system is 6,029.9 kVA under the base case scenario. The ANFIS model predicts an average forecasted load of 6,071.5 kVA, reflecting a slight increase compared to the base case. To assess the performance of the forecasting model, five key metrics are considered: MAE, MAPE, MSE, RMSE, and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The computed values for these metrics are as follows: MAE = 7.7611, MAPE = 0.14401, MSE = 0.6399, RMSE = 0.79993, and $R^2 = 0.99993$. These results indicate that the forecasted values are exceptionally close to the actual values, with minimal deviation. The findings underscore the remarkable accuracy and reliability of the ANFIS model, confirming its effectiveness as a robust tool for predicting system load in the RDN.

4.2.2. ANNs. The average forecasted load from the ANN prediction model is 6,105.7 kVA, slightly higher than both the base case load and the result from ANFIS. The performance metrics for the model are as follows: MAE = 31.4114, MAPE = 1.631%, MSE = 109.55, RMSE = 10.467, and $R^2 = 0.98797$. These values indicate that the forecasted loads are reasonably close to the actual values, with the MAPE suggesting a moderate level of deviation. Although the ANN model shows a slight decrease in accuracy compared to ANFIS, it still effectively captures the overall trend of the system load. Overall, these metrics demonstrate that the ANN model provides reasonably accurate predictions, with only minor deviations from the actual values. Figure 9 illustrates the load prediction results of the radial distribution system using both ANFIS and ANN, compared to the actual test dataset. Figure 9 demonstrates the load prediction results of the radial distribution system using ANFIS and ANN, compared with the test (actual) dataset.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the ANFIS model is more effective in predicting the system load for the radial distribution system. The lower RMSE and MAPE values associated with ANFIS suggest that it offers a more reliable and precise forecast compared to the ANN model. This can be attributed to ANFIS's ability to integrate fuzzy logic with neural network learning, capturing the nonlinear relationships in the data more effectively than the traditional ANN approach. Thus, ANFIS is recommended for load forecasting in this context due to its superior performance in minimizing forecasting errors.

4.3. Performance Evaluation Using PSO

4.3.1. System Power Loss. In the base case scenario, the system's performance is characterized by an active power

loss of 399.684 kW and a reactive power loss of 265.44 kVAr. This baseline measurement provides a reference point for evaluating the effects of different forecasting models and DG operation using PSO on distribution system performance. When ANFIS is used for load forecasting, the active and reactive power losses increase to 482.3738 kW and 320.602 kVAr, respectively. This represents a significant rise compared to the base case. The increase in power loss suggests that while ANFIS forecasts the load higher than the base case values, it also introduces additional stress on the network, leading to greater energy dissipation.

The use of ANN for load forecasting results in active and reactive power losses of 485.308 kW and 322.542 kVAr, respectively. This is higher than the loss observed with the ANFIS forecast. The increased power loss in the ANN scenario underscores the higher forecast errors associated with this model, which exacerbate network inefficiencies and energy dissipation.

With the integration and optimal operation of DG into the radial distribution system, the active and reactive power losses are significantly reduced to 56.0881 kW and 33.15 kVAr, respectively. This substantial decrease demonstrates the effectiveness of DG placement in alleviating power losses. By introducing DG and implementing PSO, the system benefits from enhanced local generation capabilities, which help reduce overall energy dissipation and improve efficiency.

The analysis reveals that both ANFIS and ANN forecasting methods lead to higher active power losses compared to the base case, with ANN forecasts resulting in the highest loss. This suggests that both forecasting models, while useful for predicting load, also introduce additional stress on the network. In contrast, the integration of DG and the implementation of PSO into the system leads to a significant reduction in power loss, highlighting their role in enhancing system performance and efficiency. Figures 10 and 11 demonstrate the active and reactive power losses at different loads and operating conditions.

4.3.2. AVDI. In the base case scenario, the AVDI is 0.0063929. This value reflects the degree of voltage deviation from the nominal voltage across the system. A lower AVDI indicates good voltage regulation and stability under base load conditions, suggesting that the system maintains its voltage levels within acceptable limits with minimal deviation.

When the ANFIS is used for load forecasting, the AVDI increases to 0.0077562. This increase signifies a slight deterioration in voltage regulation compared to the base case. The higher AVDI value indicates that the load forecasts provided by ANFIS introduce some additional voltage deviation, though the impact is relatively moderate.

The AVDI for the ANN forecasting model is 0.0078024. This value is slightly higher than that for ANFIS and suggests a further decline in voltage stability. The higher AVDI observed with ANN forecasts points to greater voltage deviations, likely due to the less accurate load predictions provided by the ANN model compared to ANFIS.

FIGURE 9: Load prediction result.

FIGURE 10: The active power loss at different load conditions and using DG.

In contrast, with the integration of DG and its optimal operation using PSO, the AVDI improves significantly to 0.00015955. This substantial reduction in the AVDI indicates a marked improvement in voltage regulation and stability. The presence of DG and its optimal operation in the distribution network enhances local voltage support, reducing deviations and achieving nearly optimal voltage conditions.

The evaluation of the AVDI across different scenarios reveals that both ANFIS and ANN forecasting methods lead to a slight increase in voltage deviations compared to the base case, with the ANN forecasting model resulting in the highest AVDI, reflecting the largest impact on voltage stability. In contrast, the integration of DG results in a dramatic

improvement in voltage regulation, with the AVDI approaching near-optimal levels. This demonstrates the effectiveness of DG in enhancing voltage stability and highlights its critical role in improving overall system performance. Figure 12 illustrates the validity of this discussion.

4.3.3. VSI. In the base case scenario, the VSI is 0.58133. This value indicates the level of voltage stability within the network under base load conditions. A VSI of 0.58133 suggests that the system maintains a moderate level of voltage stability, reflecting the system’s ability to handle voltage variations within acceptable limits without significant instability.

FIGURE 11: The reactive power loss at different load conditions and using DG.

FIGURE 12: The AVDI values at different loads and using DG.

When forecasting with the ANFIS, the VSI decreases to 0.54848. This reduction in VSI signifies a decline in voltage stability compared to the base case. The lower VSI value implies that the network faces greater challenges in maintaining stable voltage levels due to the increased load forecasted by ANFIS.

The VSI for the ANN forecasting model is 0.54761, which is slightly lower than the VSI with the ANFIS forecast. This further decrease indicates an additional decline in voltage stability, reflecting the less accurate load predictions from the ANN model. As the VSI is lower compared to both the base case and ANFIS forecasts, this suggests that the ANN model introduces more significant stability issues.

On the other hand, with the integration of DG and the application of PSO, the VSI improves significantly to 0.9186. This substantial increase indicates a major enhancement in voltage stability.

The analysis of the VSI across different scenarios highlights the impact of forecasting methods and optimization strategies on voltage stability. Both the ANFIS and ANN forecasting methods result in a decrease in VSI compared to the base case, with ANN forecasts causing the most significant decline. In contrast, the integration of DG combined with PSO optimization leads to a substantial improvement in VSI, indicating enhanced voltage stability.

The optimal operation of DG, identified through PSO, greatly improves the system's ability to maintain stable voltage levels across the network, as shown in Figure 13.

4.3.4. LOLP. In the base case scenario, the LOLP is 0.7827. This value represents the probability of experiencing a loss of load and provides an indication of the system's reliability under normal operating conditions. An LOLP of 0.7827 suggests that the likelihood of encountering load loss is relatively high, reflecting low network reliability.

When the ANFIS is used for load forecasting, the LOLP increases slightly to 0.7960. This increase in LOLP indicates a marginal decline in system reliability compared to the base case. The higher LOLP value reflects a slightly greater probability of load loss under the ANFIS forecasted load conditions.

The use of the ANN for forecasting results in a further increase in LOLP to 0.7962. This value is slightly higher than the one observed with the ANFIS forecasts, indicating a further reduction in system reliability. The increased LOLP with ANN forecasts suggests a higher probability of load loss due to less accurate load predictions, exacerbating the network's reliability issues.

With the integration of DG and the implementation of PSO, the LOLP improves significantly to 0.3612. This substantial reduction demonstrates a marked improvement in system reliability.

The analysis of LOLP across different scenarios provides insight into the impact of forecasting methods and optimization strategies on system reliability. Both the ANFIS and ANN forecasting methods lead to an increase in LOLP compared to the base case, with ANN forecasts resulting in the highest LOLP, indicating reduced system reliability. In contrast, the integration of DG combined with PSO optimization significantly lowers the LOLP, reflecting improved system reliability.

The strategic placement of DG, identified through PSO, is crucial in achieving this enhancement, demonstrating the effectiveness of DG integration and optimization in improving network performance and reliability. The optimal operation of DG using PSO effectively reduces the probability of load loss, thereby enhancing the network's overall reliability and performance, as shown in Figure 14.

4.3.5. ENS. The simulation results provide a comprehensive overview of the ENS from the radial distribution system under different load scenarios and the integration of DG in the network using PSO, as shown in Figure 15. In the base case scenario, the ENS by the distribution network is 720.4087 MWh/year. This value increases to 780.5329 MWh/year when the ANFIS load forecasting model is implemented.

The use of the ANN for load forecasting results in a further increase in ENS to 781.2355 MWh/year. This value is slightly higher than that observed with ANFIS forecasts, indicating a further reduction in system reliability. The increased ENS with ANN forecasts suggests a lower

reliability due to less accurate load predictions, exacerbating the network's reliability issues.

However, with the integration of DG and the implementation of PSO, the ENS improves significantly to 332.4792 MWh/year. This substantial reduction demonstrates that the integration of DG using PSO is highly effective in enhancing energy supply reliability.

Overall, the results indicate that while the load prediction using ANFIS and ANN models showed lower power supply reliability, advanced optimization techniques like PSO in DG's optimal operation within the RDN provide a more efficient solution for minimizing energy supply shortfalls, as demonstrated in Figure 15.

4.3.6. AENS. The AENS is also another reliability measurement index of a distribution system. The simulation results provide a comprehensive overview of the AENS to each customer from the radial distribution system under different load scenarios and the integration of DG in the network using PSO. The base case scenario revealed that the AENS per customer is 0.253 MWh/year. This figure rises to 0.273 MWh/year when an ANFIS load forecast model is implemented. The use of the ANN for load forecasting results in a further increase of the AENS to 0.274 MWh/year. This value is slightly higher than that observed with ANFIS forecasts, indicating a further reduction in system reliability. The increased AENS with ANN forecasts suggests a lower reliability value due to less accurate load predictions, aggravating the network's reliability issues.

With the integration of DG and the implementation of PSO, the AENS improves significantly to 0.117 MWh/year. This considerable reduction demonstrates that the integration of DG using PSO is highly effective in enhancing energy supply reliability. Overall, the results indicate that while the load prediction result using ANFIS and ANN showed a lower power supply reliability value, advanced optimization techniques like PSO in DG optimal operation in the RDN provide a more efficient solution for minimizing energy supply shortfalls as shown in Figure 16.

4.4. Impact of Load Variation and Optimal DG Placement on Voltage Profile. The simulation results in Figures 17 and 18 provide a detailed comparison of voltage performance across various scenarios, highlighting the impact of different load prediction techniques. In the base case, the voltage values ranged from 1.000 to 0.87318, showing a steady decline as the demand increased. When the ANN load forecasting approach was applied, the voltage values declined further, ranging from 1.000 to 0.86024, indicating a slight reduction in the voltage profile compared to the base case. Similarly, the ANFIS load forecasting scenario resulted in voltage values that were slightly lower than those of the base case, ranging from 0.86058 to 1.000.

These results suggest that while both ANN and ANFIS forecasting methods lead to a minor reduction in voltage stability, the overall impact on voltage performance remains manageable. However, the application of these forecasting models still highlights the importance of maintaining

FIGURE 13: The VSI values at different load conditions and using DG.

FIGURE 14: The LOLP values at different load conditions and using DG.

FIGURE 15: The ENS values at different loads and using DG.

FIGURE 16: The AENS values at different load conditions and using DG.

FIGURE 17: Voltage profile at different load scenarios.

effective load prediction techniques to minimize voltage instability in the system.

In contrast, the optimal operation of DG in the radial distribution system using the PSO algorithm demonstrated a noticeable improvement in voltage stability. The voltage profile in this scenario ranged from 0.979 to 1.0037, consistently higher than those observed in both the ANN and ANFIS load prediction cases. This improvement is quantified by the voltage improvement metric, which indicates the percentage increase in voltage stability relative to the base case. The incorporation of DG in the radial distribution system resulted in a maximum voltage improvement of 14.901%, underscoring its effectiveness in enhancing voltage levels.

Overall, these results highlight that while ANN and ANFIS load prediction methods lead to a reduction in the voltage profile of the radial distribution system, the integration of DG significantly enhances voltage stability. This demonstrates that DG, when optimally integrated using PSO, provides a more robust solution for improving the performance and reliability of energy systems.

4.5. Fitness Function. The simulation results provide a detailed assessment of the fitness function across different scenarios, illustrating their respective impacts on optimizing the system. In the base case (base load), the fitness function value was recorded at 4.3254, serving as a benchmark for

FIGURE 18: Voltage profile improvement using DG and PSO.

FIGURE 19: The fitness function curve.

performance evaluation. The ANFIS-based load forecasting scenario yielded a fitness function value of 5.1711, indicating lower fitness compared to the base case and falling short of optimal performance. The ANN load forecasting scenario showed an even lower fitness function value of 5.2008, suggesting slightly worse performance compared to both the ANFIS and base case results, as demonstrated in Figure 19.

In contrast, the optimal operation of DG in a radial distribution system using PSO achieved a significantly higher fitness function value of 0.753. This substantial improvement demonstrates the superior efficiency and effectiveness of integrating DG using the PSO algorithm, highlighting its capacity to optimize system performance far more effectively than the other scenarios. The results underscore the substantial advantages of the DG and PSO approach in achieving optimal system operation and efficiency.

5. Conclusion

This study makes a significant contribution by conducting a comprehensive performance evaluation of an 11-bus, 15 kV RDN in Ethiopia, employing PSO to optimize network performance while evaluating the impact of load forecasting models and DG integration. The research highlights the superior forecasting accuracy of the ANFIS over ANN and provides valuable insights into critical network performance metrics, such as power loss, voltage stability, and energy supply, while identifying key areas for future research to address uncertainties in renewable energy sources and dynamic control strategies.

ANFIS significantly outperformed ANN, achieving considerably lower values for MAE, MAPE, MSE, and RMSE, along with a higher coefficient of determination (R^2). These results highlight ANFIS's exceptional accuracy in load

forecasting, which is critical for ensuring efficient and reliable network operation.

The study further examined key network performance metrics—such as power loss, VSI, AVDI, LOLP, ENS, and AENS—under both base and forecasted load conditions. The findings revealed that integrating forecasted load data, particularly from ANN, negatively impacted network performance, increasing power losses and reducing VSI. This emphasizes the critical role of accurate load forecasting in maintaining optimal network stability and efficiency.

Moreover, the PSO algorithm demonstrated considerable effectiveness in enhancing the network's performance, showing that PSO, when combined with reliable load forecasts, can substantially optimize system operations and improve overall efficiency.

Looking ahead, future research could explore alternative optimization techniques, such as gray wolf optimization (GWO) or hybrid models, to further enhance the optimization process. Expanding these forecasting and optimization methods to more complex systems, such as the IEEE 300-bus network, would offer valuable insights into their applicability to large-scale operations. Additionally, challenges related to data preprocessing, model selection, and computational costs should be addressed in future work to improve the practicality and scalability of both forecasting and optimization techniques in real-world scenarios.

In conclusion, this study strongly advocates for the use of ANFIS for load forecasting due to its superior accuracy and recommends the continued application of PSO for network optimization to drive sustained improvements in system performance.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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